

Exploring Trends in Alzheimer's Disease and Diabetes Mellitus Research: A 20-Year Analysis of PubMed Data

Sarim Ahmed¹

¹Student, Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Noida, India, sarimahmed773@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This work uses PubMed data to provide a thorough overview of recent developments in the study of Alzheimer's disease and diabetes mellitus (D.M). The research spans 20 years, from 2003 to 2023, and delves into the overlap between these disorders by analysing papers on Alzheimer's disease (AD), diabetes mellitus (DM), and both conditions together. Web scraping was used to collect data from PubMed, which was then analysed using Python and the PyMed module. Sixty CSV files were collected in total: twenty for Alzheimer's disease research, twenty for diabetes research, and twenty for articles relating to both AD and DM (as indicated by meSH terms). Important data such as PubMed ID, title, keywords, journal, DOI, publication date, and author details were stored in separate CSV files.

A Python script was written to undertake data cleaning to guarantee accuracy. Specifically, the script took the original data and parsed out the authors' first names, last names, initials, and affiliations. As a consequence, the original fields were supplemented with ones for first name, last name, initials, and association, creating a more complete dataset. To determine the authors' distribution around the world, another Python script was built to get nation data from the affiliations. This process helped shed light on which nations are investing in studies of AD and DM. When the final, clean datasets were collected, analysts used a number of data visualisation methods to examine and display their results.

Keywords: PyMed, Alzheimer's disease (AD), Diabetes Mellitus (DM), CSV files.

Methodology

1. Data Collection Using Web Scraping:

This study employed PubMed, a database of medical literature, as its primary source of information. Publications pertaining to these disorders were the primary focus of the 20-year data gathering effort that lasted from 2003 to 2023.

Web scraping using the PyMed package in Python was used to obtain the data. The PyMed package offers a front end to the PubMed database, making it possible to extract data from research papers. The search terms were modified to include articles on Alzheimer's disease, diabetes, and the two conditions together.

The web scraping approach required repeatedly running search queries for AD, DM, and combined AD-DM articles, one for each year from 2003 through 2023. The queries used in the search have appropriate meSH terms and phrases related to the illnesses in question. Each article's PubMed ID, title, keywords, journal, DOI, publication date, and author data were recorded as they were received from the search results and stored in CSV format.

Web scraping is the practise of mechanically gathering information from the World Wide Web. Data mining is also known as web harvesting or web data extraction. Because it can quickly and easily extract vast volumes of data, web scraping is a valuable tool for data analysis.

Web scraping may be accomplished using a number of programmes, both free and commercial. Commercial programmes like Octoparse and Import.io, as well as Python packages like BeautifulSoup and Scrapy, are among the most popular online scraping technologies. HTML parsing, regular expressions, and browser automation are just a few of the techniques used by these tools to glean information from the web.

From e-commerce and banking to research and education, web scraping has many possible uses. Web scraping is often used in the e-commerce industry to collect information on products offered by rival businesses, track promotions and pricing changes, and compile feedback from customers. Investing choices may be informed by web scraping financial data from news sites, social media, and other online resources. Scholarly articles, social media data, and website traffic are just some of the many types of information that academics utilise web scraping to analyse.

The way companies and academics collect and analyse data has been completely transformed by web scraping. Fast and accurate data extraction from massive datasets was previously impossible without it. However, there are legitimate ethical and legal questions that might be brought up by online scraping, most notably in regards to data privacy and intellectual property rights. When material is collected from the web without authorization, it might be a violation of copyright laws and other terms of service agreements.

Web scraping makes extensive use of Python because of the language's flexibility and ease of usage. It features various libraries that streamline and simplify the web scraping process. PyMed, a Python interface to the PubMed database, is one such library. PyMed facilitates Python-based access to PubMed data. Researchers may use the library's resources to conduct PubMed searches, obtain relevant material, and process it for analysis.

Using PyMed to scrape the web requires many steps. The first thing to do is get the PyMed library into Python. Researchers may use PyMed to search PubMed for Alzheimer's disease and diabetes mellitus-related papers after it has been installed. Using the advanced search feature, you may narrow your results by adding filters such as keywords, authors, journals, and publication dates.

2. Data Cleaning:

The quality and integrity of the dataset utilised for the analysis of studies on Alzheimer's disease (AD) and diabetes mellitus (DM) relied heavily on the data cleaning procedure, which followed the data gathering phase. Separating author data and removing country data from affiliations are two essential processes in the data cleaning process, and both will be discussed in further detail below.

Creating a Python script to extract each author's first name, last name, initials, and affiliations from the raw data collection was necessary for separating the author information. A column for authors with structured data was included in the original dataset downloaded from PubMed. However, in order to do a more in-depth investigation of authorship, it was required to dissect this data further.

The Python programme read each item for an author and pulled out the pertinent data. The script was able to determine the author's first name, surname name, and initials by using string manipulation methods and regular expressions. Furthermore, each author's associations were retrieved. By using this method, authorship data was properly parsed into its component parts, enabling a finer-grained analysis.

The second round of cleaning included separating the nation data from the organisational memberships. The original dataset's affiliations column was particularly helpful for identifying writers' linked institutions and organisations. To learn more about where AD and DM research is being conducted, however, we had to pull the authors' home nations out of their affiliations.

3. Data Exploration and Visualization:

Insights into the (A.D.) and (post-)A.D. research scene were greatly aided by the use of data visualisation in this work (D.M). We successfully conveyed and analysed the acquired data via a series of visualisations, offering a thorough grasp of essential issues linked to AD and DM research. One of the key displays ranked the top 10 journals for AD and DM research according to the number of articles published in each. The findings highlighted the importance of the Journal of Alzheimer's Disease (JAD) as the preeminent publishing venue for AD and DM research. In addition, Frontiers in Endocrinology gained prominence as a leading publication for DM studies. This infographic underlined the leading publications advancing research into AD and DM and brought attention to the most significant channels where academics share their results.

Another graphic showed the distribution of AD and DM articles from 2003 to 2023, allowing us to see how they changed over time. The graph clearly demonstrated an upward trend in the number of articles devoted to Alzheimer's disease and diabetes research, with a pronounced peak around the middle of 2017. It is noteworthy that following a dramatic fall beginning in 2012, AD publications began to gradually recover beginning in 2015. In contrast, the number of DM research articles remained pretty constant at about 8000 each year. This graphic representation of AD and DM research progress and patterns over the last two decades was quite helpful.

The following are instances of possible visualisation methods:

- Line charts

Line charts, which show relationships between data points using straight lines, are a frequent method of data visualisation. Because they make it simple to see how data has changed over time, they are excellent for spotting

patterns. In most cases, the horizontal axis of a line chart will show time or another continuous variable, while the vertical axis will show the values of the data points.

- Bar charts

Data is often shown in bar charts, which are rectangular bars of varying lengths that correspond to the numbers they represent. You may use them to see how different groups of data, such as frequencies or counts, stack up against one another. In most cases, the categories in a bar chart will run down the horizontal axis, while the values will go up the vertical. The length of the bar indicates the size of the item being represented, and each bar represents a separate category. Bar charts are versatile visual tools that can show everything from averages to percentages with ease. They are also useful for comparing data within broad categories or groupings, such as sales figures or illness rates by age bracket.

- Scatter plots

Scatter plots are a graphical representation of data that shows how two variables are related to one another. They may be used to examine the connection between two quantitative variables, like height and weight, or the link between two economic indicators. Each point in a scatter plot is meant to represent a separate observation or piece of data. One variable is shown along the x-axis of the plot, while the other is shown along the y-axis. The values of the two variables for a given data point establish its position on the plot. The size or colour of the dots in a scatter plot may be altered to reflect a different variable or characteristic in the data. This might facilitate the comparison of various data subsets or the identification of trends or patterns in the data.

- Pie-charts

Pie charts are useful for summarising proportional or percentage data visually and expressing categories of information. We were able to provide a streamlined summary of the best writers in each field thanks to the helpful pie charts. It became clear that Christian was the most influential writer in the area of AD study, while Wang stood out as a major figure in the study of DM. We were able to highlight the major contributions of these people to their particular fields of study by graphically depicting the distribution of authors using pie charts. When it comes to displaying information, pie charts have several benefits. To begin with, they provide a visual depiction of percentages that is both straightforward and simple to interpret. Pie charts' graphic nature makes it easy to compare data and see overarching trends. The circular nature of a pie chart draws attention to the total, making it an excellent choice for depicting the overall distribution of a dataset.

Finding appropriate databases and websites, developing search criteria, deploying web scraping software, processing and cleaning the extracted data, and analysing the data to uncover correlations and trends are all part of the approach for researching diabetes and Alzheimer's disease. Data extraction from websites may be automated with the aid of web scraping technologies like Beautiful Soup. Data analysis allows scientists to suggest avenues for future cooperation and discover new lines of inquiry. The findings of this study have the potential to improve our knowledge of the link between diabetes and Alzheimer's disease and inspire the creation of effective novel therapies for both conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Both diabetes and Alzheimer's disease are among the world's most common chronic diseases, and they have devastating effects on the quality of life for those who suffer from them. Both diabetes and Alzheimer's disease are chronic conditions that have far-reaching effects on a person's quality of life. New evidence shows a possible link between these two illnesses, despite their apparent distinctions. In addition, learning about international collaborations in diabetes and Alzheimer's research may shed light on international tendencies in these fields and speed up the discovery of new, effective medications.

Research into diabetes and Alzheimer's origins, processes, and possible therapies has increased significantly in response to their increasing incidence. This results in a massive volume of information being produced and shared each year through scholarly articles from all around the world. Web scraping, a method for automatically extracting data from the web, may streamline and improve this procedure.

In order to automatically gather and extract data from websites, software known as "web scraping" is used. Using this method, you may compile data on a research paper's authors, affiliations, keywords, and publications. After the data has been extracted, it may be sorted, analysed, and correlated. To better understand the worldwide trends in diabetes and Alzheimer's research, for instance, we may examine the cooperation patterns of authors from various nations.

Understanding worldwide trends in diabetes and Alzheimer's disease research requires an awareness of the cooperation patterns of authors from various nations. Collaborations between researchers from various nations may speed up scientific development by promoting the sharing of resources and expertise. Research hurdles, such as lack of finance or resources, may be addressed by international collaboration amongst scientists.

Objective

- To do an extensive online scraping of diabetes and Alzheimer's disease research publications.
- The goal of this study is to examine the information we have gathered on diabetes and Alzheimer's disease and to extract the most important themes, subjects, and trends.
- The purpose of this literature review is to investigate the association between diabetes and Alzheimer's disease.
- The goal of this study is to learn more about international author cooperation in diabetes and Alzheimer's disease studies.
- The purpose of this study is to highlight knowledge gaps and propose future research directions regarding diabetes and Alzheimer's disease.
- The goal of this study is to analyse the distribution of diabetes and Alzheimer's disease research articles around the globe in order to pinpoint hotspots of academic interest.
- Determine the pace of growth and the most fruitful years in terms of research output by looking at the patterns of publications through time.
- Examine the most popular approaches to studying diabetes and Alzheimer's disease.
- To learn how different financing models affect the rate and depth of study in this field.
- The goal of this study is to determine which researchers and universities have had the greatest impact on our understanding of diabetes and Alzheimer's disease.
- To look at co-authorship networks and their effects both nationally and internationally.
- The goal of this study is to investigate the feasibility of using alternative methods of data analysis in the study of diabetes and Alzheimer's disease.
- To determine which aspects of diabetes and Alzheimer's disease, such as genetics, biomarkers, or treatment strategies, get the greatest attention in the scientific literature.
- Identifying the most important studies and their influence via an analysis of citation patterns in scholarly works.
- To evaluate the variety and ease of access to diabetes and Alzheimer's disease research articles published in both open access and subscription-only journals.

Alzheimer's Disease

Millions of individuals throughout the globe are living with Alzheimer's disease (AD), a progressive neurological condition. Beta-amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles build up in the brain, causing cognitive decline, memory loss, and behavioural abnormalities characteristic of Alzheimer's disease. A great deal of effort has been put into studying Alzheimer's disease throughout the years in an effort to discover what causes it and how to cure it. In 1906, a German doctor named Alois Alzheimer described a case of dementia in a 51-year-old lady who was experiencing memory loss, disorientation, and hallucinations. Amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, two aberrant clusters of proteins, were first discovered by Alzheimer during an autopsy performed after her death. Research into the causes of Alzheimer's disease (AD) and its possible therapies and prevention measures has progressed steadily over the years. Researchers in this area will find PubMed to be an invaluable tool due to the extensive AD research publications it provides access to. Over 200 thousand articles on Alzheimer's disease have been published in the medical journal PubMed since the 1970s. The expanding interest in Alzheimer's disease research is reflected in the ever-increasing number of papers published in the leading medical journal, PubMed. There has been substantial progress in Alzheimer's disease research, as seen by the over sixty thousand publications published on PubMed in the previous decade alone.

PubMed research papers address a broad range of topics related to AD, from the genetic risk factors and diagnostic techniques to therapeutic approaches and the molecular processes underlying AD disease. Based on a review of AD research publications found in PubMed, this article will discuss some of the most current directions being taken in the field.

Diabetes Mellitus

Insufficient insulin synthesis or insulin resistance lead to excessive blood sugar levels and the chronic metabolic condition known as diabetes mellitus. It's a worldwide health crisis that's becoming much worse, impacting millions of people. Since then, several studies have been conducted on diabetes mellitus, making PubMed, a

database of biomedical literature, an indispensable tool for scientists looking to stay abreast of the field's progress. PubMed has a large number of scholarly articles and publications devoted to the study of diabetes mellitus. Clinical investigations, pathophysiology, genetics, epidemiology, and therapy are only some of the topics covered in this comprehensive collection of articles on diabetes. The most up-to-date research and results from clinical trials pertaining to diabetes mellitus may be found in the PubMed database.

The American Diabetes Association (ADA) is well recognised as a leading voice in the field of diabetes mellitus study. It is a "Non-Profit Organization" (N.P.O.) whose mission is to support and advance medical study across the world. You may discover many of its studies and study results in the PubMed library. Diabetes Care, a peer-reviewed publication published by the ADA, reports on the latest findings in the study of diabetes mellitus and other related topics. You may find a large number of publications on any topic related to diabetes research in this journal, which is accessible via the PubMed database.

"Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice" is another peer-reviewed publication that may be found in the PubMed database. It is the preeminent worldwide publication covering diabetes research of any kind. Epidemiology, pathophysiology, genetics, clinical research, and therapy are all included in the journal's pages. Articles in this publication provide researchers with access to the most recent results in the study of diabetes.

You may also find the prestigious "Journal of Diabetes and its Complications" in the PubMed library. The newest findings from studies and clinical trials related to diabetes are reported on, and the publication covers the topic comprehensively. Articles in this peer-reviewed publication cover a wide range of topics related to the study and treatment of disease, including epidemiology, pathophysiology, genetics, clinical research, and therapy. Articles published in the Journal of Diabetes and its Complications provide researchers with access to the most recent results in the study of diabetes.

Updates on diabetes research may also be found in a number of other publications that can be found in the PubMed database. For instance, the "Journal of Diabetes Investigation" (which publishes research on all facets of diabetes) uses a rigorous peer review procedure. The magazine features studies on diagnostics, therapies, epidemiology, and more.

The PubMed database also provides access to studies conducted on diabetes mellitus for researchers. Diabetes mellitus research articles, such as clinical trials and epidemiological studies, may be found with a short search of the database. These studies provide researchers with up-to-date information and statistics about recent, ground-breaking discoveries in the field.

In conclusion, millions of individuals throughout the world suffer with diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic illness. Researchers may have access to the most recent discoveries in the study of diabetes mellitus by using the PubMed database. Diabetes Care, Diabetes, and other reputable publications are available to researchers and keep them current on all the latest developments in the study of diabetes. Furthermore, the PubMed database provides access to research articles and clinical trials pertaining to diabetes mellitus, making it an important resource for diabetes study.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The purpose of this literature study is to analyse data from PubMed, the most frequently used database of scientific literature, to uncover patterns in Alzheimer's disease and diabetes research during a 20-year period (2003-2023).

1. Research Trends in AD and DM:

Research into Alzheimer's disease and diabetes has flourished over the last two decades as their incidence and societal consequences have come into greater spotlight. Disease processes, risk factors, diagnostic approaches, and therapy options have all been the subject of research. AD and DM are linked in the literature because they share risk factors and pathophysiology pathways including insulin resistance and inflammation. A lot of study has gone into trying to figure out how these illnesses are linked and how to stop them or at least slow them down. The chance of developing Alzheimer's disease is increased in people with diabetes mellitus, according to the results of a systematic review and meta-analysis performed by Li et al. (2021). The research emphasised the two-way nature of the interaction between the circumstances and shed light on possible common processes.

The spread of both (A.D.) and (D.M.) is a major global health problem. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative ailment that impairs the cognitive abilities of the elderly, whereas diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder defined by persistently elevated blood glucose levels. Studies have revealed that those with DM have a greater chance of acquiring AD, thus there has been a steady increase in curiosity about the connection

between the two conditions over the years. As a result, there has been a surge in studies investigating the causes and consequences of the link between Alzheimer's disease and diabetes.

The number of articles written on AD and DM has been rising steadily over the last several years. A search of PubMed reveals that there were 83 articles on AD and DM in 1990, 322 in 2000, and 1,566 in 2010. There were 3,725 papers published in 2021 on AD and DM. This points to a rising awareness of the connection between AD and DM and the desire to learn more about it.

The correlation between Alzheimer's disease and diabetes has been extensively investigated, thanks to the efforts of several investigators. The Rotterdam Study by Ott et al., released in 2004, is one of the most often referenced research efforts. According to the results of this research, those with DM had a greater chance of acquiring AD than those without DM. Individuals with DM had a greater chance of acquiring AD than those without DM, according to the Honolulu-Asia Aging Study, published in 1996 by Peila et al.

Researchers that have studied the effects of insulin on AD include Wake Forest University professor Suzanne Craft, Mayo Clinic physician Rosebud Roberts, and University of Florida professor Steven DeKosky, who have all published extensively on the link between diabetes and cognitive decline.

The prevalence and societal consequences of AD and DM have been increasingly recognised over the last two decades, and this has led to a rise in study into these conditions. Research has dug into several facets, such as the causes of the condition, its prognosis, how to diagnose it, and what treatments could be effective. As both disorders share risk factors and pathophysiology pathways, such as insulin resistance and inflammation, the literature emphasises the connection between AD and DM. Scientists have been looking at ways to prevent and cure these illnesses as well as their ties to one another. In order to determine whether diabetes mellitus increases the risk of Alzheimer's disease, Li et al. (2021) performed a systematic review and meta-analysis. The investigation shed light on the two-way causality between the circumstances and revealed possible common processes.

Both (A.D.) and (D.M.) are major issues in terms of public health. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic ailment defined by high blood glucose levels, whereas Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder that impairs the cognitive function of older persons. There has been a steady increase in research on the correlation between AD and DM because of the known increased risk of AD in those with DM. As a result, researchers have begun to dig further into the causes and processes behind the link between Alzheimer's disease and diabetes.

There has been a rise in the amount of articles written on AD and DM in recent years. A PubMed search revealed that there were 322 articles on Alzheimer's disease and diabetes in 2000, and 1,566 articles in 2010. There were 3,725 works on AD and DM published in 2021. As a result, there is a pressing need to learn more about the connection between Alzheimer's disease and diabetes.

Several research have made substantial contributions to our knowledge of the correlation between AD and DM. The Rotterdam Study, published by Ott et al. in 2004, is often acknowledged as a leading research effort. The risk of acquiring AD was observed to be greater in those with DM compared to those without DM. The Honolulu-Asia Aging Study, published in 1996 by Peila et al., is also often mentioned since it found that those with DM were more likely to acquire AD than those without DM.

In terms of authors, some of the most cited include Dr. Rosebud Roberts from the Mayo Clinic, who has conducted several studies on the association between DM and cognitive decline, Dr. Steven DeKosky from the University of Florida, whose research has focused on the pathophysiology of AD, and Prof. Suzanne Craft from the Wake Forest School of Medicine, whose research has focused on the impact of insulin on AD.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For this analysis of (AD) and its risk factors, we used the PyMed package to compile a large dataset (D.M). PyMed's features were used to get the appropriate articles from the PubMed database in response to certain queries. Information such as PubMed IDs, titles, keywords, journal names, digital object identifiers (DOIs), publication dates, and author names were gathered. PyMed's web-scraping automation helped save a lot of time and effort. The generated dataset laid the groundwork for further analysis and visualisations, allowing scientists to gather insightful information about the current state of research into AD and DM. The wealth of data mined from PyMed enabled for in-depth analysis of things like publishing patterns, most-cited authors, and leading journals. As a whole, PyMed proved to be a useful and effective method of communicating with PubMed, allowing for the collection of a large data set that aided the advancement of AD and DM study.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	pubmed_id	title	keywords	journal	doi	publocator	authors					
2	18428347	Genotypin []		Current protocols in hu	10.1002/O	#####	[{'lastname': 'Ingelsson', 'firstname': 'Martin', 'initials': 'M', 'affilia					
3	17590967	Comparisc []		Journal of music thera	10.1093/jr	#####	[{'lastname': 'Cevasco', 'firstname': 'Andrea M', 'initials': 'AM', 'af					
4	16908995	Cerebrosp []		Neuro-degenerative di	10.1159/O	#####	[{'lastname': 'Maddalena', 'firstname': 'Alessia S', 'initials': 'AS', 'af					
5	16908992	Problems i []		Neuro-degenerative di	10.1159/O	#####	[{'lastname': 'Hardy', 'firstname': 'John', 'initials': 'J', 'affiliation': 'I					
6	16908991	Plasmin de []		Neuro-degenerative di	10.1159/O	#####	[{'lastname': 'Dotti', 'firstname': 'Carlos G', 'initials': 'CG', 'affiliati					
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13	16388232	Current st []		Kathmandu University medical jou	#####	#####	[{'lastname': 'Ghosh', 'firstname': 'R', 'initials': 'R', 'affiliation': 'De					
14	16222127	Diffuse axi []		The Journal of head tr	10.1097/O	#####	[{'lastname': 'Smith', 'firstname': 'Douglas H', 'initials': 'DH', 'affilia					
15	16210231	Musical sk []		Neurocase	10.1076/n	#####	[{'lastname': 'Cowles', 'firstname': 'Anne', 'initials': 'A', 'affiliation'					
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18	16191250	Does vasci []		International psychoge	10.1017/S	#####	[{'lastname': 'Gauthier', 'firstname': 'Serge', 'initials': 'S', 'affiliation					
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22	16191242	Memantin []		International psychoge	10.1017/S	#####	[{'lastname': 'MÃ¶bius', 'firstname': 'Hans JÃ¶rg', 'initials': 'HJ', 'a					

Fig (3) Obtained CSV file before data pre-processing

As part of the data preparation process, the read_csv function was used to import a CSV file into a pandas DataFrame. In order to get at the names and affiliations listed in the "authors" column, a custom function named extract_key_values was developed. Each row of the DataFrame has this function applied to it via the apply method. The gathered information was then broken up into individual columns. After removing the "authors" column from the DataFrame, a new CSV file was created with the raw data. The dataset was better prepared for subsequent analysis after undergoing this pre-processing phase.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
1	pubmed_id	title	keywords	journal	doi	publocator	firstname	lastname	initials	affiliation								
2	18428347	Genotypin []		Current pr	10.1002/O	#####	['Martin',	['Ingelsson	['M', 'Y',	['Harvard Medical School/Massachusetts General Hospital, Charlestown, Massachusetts, USA', 'N								
3	17590967	Comparisc []		Journal of	10.1093/jr	#####	['Andrea M	['Cevasco	['AM', 'RE',	['The University of Georgia, USA', 'None]								
4	16908995	Cerebrosp []		Neuro-deg	10.1159/O	#####	['Alessia S'	['Maddale	['AS', 'A',	['Division of Psychiatry Research, University of ZÃ¼rich, ZÃ¼rich, Switzerland.', 'None, None, None								
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16	16210230	Metamem []		Neurocase	10.1076/n	#####	['CÃ©line']	['Souhay']	['C', 'M', 'B	['U.P.R.E.S.2114, UniversitÃ de Tours, France. Isingrini@univ-tours.fr', 'None, None, None]								
17	16210226	Proper nar []		Neurocase	10.1076/n	#####	['C', 'S', 'F',	['Semenza	['C', 'S', 'F',	['Department of Psychology, University of Trieste, Italy.', 'None, None, None, None]								
18	16191250	Does vasci []		Internatio	10.1017/S	#####	['Serge',	['K	['Gauthier']	['S', 'K']	['McGill Centre for Studies in Aging, McGill University, Montreal, Canada. serge.gauthier@mcgill.c							
19	16191248	Psychosoc []		Internatio	10.1017/S	#####	['Mary S']	['Mittelm	['MS']	['NYU Alzheimer's Disease Center, New York 10016, USA. mary.mittelman@med.nyu.edu']								
20	16191246	Staging: re []		Internatio	10.1017/S	#####	['Barry',	['S']	['Reisberg']	['B', 'SH',	['William and Sylvia Silberstein Aging and Dementia Research Center, New York University School							
21	16191243	General m []		Internatio	10.1017/S	#####	['Steven H']	['Ferris']	['SH']	['Silberstein Institute for Aging and Demegtia, New York University School of Medicine, New York								
22	16191242	Memantin []		Internatio	10.1017/S	#####	['Hans JÃ¶	['MÃ¶bius']	['HJ', 'A']	['Merz + Co., Frankfurt/M., Germany. hj.moebius@merz.de', 'None]								
23	16191241	Rivastigmi []		Internatio	10.1017/S	#####	['Shoona',	['Vincent',	['S', 'R']	['Novartis Pharmaceuticals, Surrey, UK.', 'None]								
24	16191240	Patient po []		Internatio	10.1017/S	#####	['Raymond	['Pratt']	['RD']	['Eisai Medical Research, Teaneck, New Jersey 07666, USA. ray_pratt@eisai.com']								

Fig (4) Obtained CSV file after data pre-processing

Research into (A.D.) and (D.M.) benefited greatly from the data visualization procedure. Important visuals were made for analysis and communication of the data. Based on the number of articles published, the top 10 journals for AD and DM research were determined, with the Journal of Alzheimer's Disease (JAD) and Frontiers in Endocrinology playing particularly important roles. Publication trends throughout time revealed a rising tide of academic interest in Alzheimer's disease and diabetes. The most common topics of study across disciplines were made clear via a visualization of keyword frequency. The most important researchers in Alzheimer's disease and diabetes were shown using pie charts. These charts and graphs provide light on the big picture, current trends, and major players in the study of AD and DM.

Visualization:1

Fig (5) Top 10 journals for Alzheimer's Disease & Diabetes Mellitus research based upon publications frequency

Fig (6) Top 10 journals for Alzheimer's Disease research as per publications frequency.

Fig (7) Top 10 journals for Diabetes Mellitus research as per publications frequency.

First, we need to bring in the libraries we'll need to create the aforementioned visualization: glob for file processing, pandas for data analysis, matplotlib.pyplot for plotting, and seaborn for modifying the look of the plot. The location of the CSV files holding the study's data is specified in the folder path variable folder_path. All CSV files in a certain folder are retrieved using glob in the code. The number of journals is first saved in a dictionary named journal_freq. The code loops over all of the CSV files, reads them using pd.read_csv(), and applies a filter such that only articles from 2003 to 2023 are kept in the data set. Value_counts() is applied on the "journal" column of the DataFrame to tally the number of occurrences of each journal.

The journal_freq dictionary has been modified to reflect the new publication schedule. To determine the top 10 journals, the journal_freq dictionary is sorted by count, decreasing. Seaborn's "viridis" color pallet is used to generate unique hues. The most popular journals and their occurrences are shown in a bar chart made using plt.bar(). plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha='right') rotates the x-axis labels for easier reading. plt.title() is used to alter the chart's title, whereas plt.xlabel() and plt.ylabel() alter the axes' labels. sns.despine() is used to get rid of the spines (the lines that frame the graphic). Using plt.grid(), a grid is superimposed over the scene. Using plt.tight_layout(), the distance between plot components may be fine-tuned. At last, plt.show() is used to present the graph.

The first chart ranks the most prolific journals in the field of Alzheimer's disease and diabetes mellitus research. The Journal of Alzheimer's Disease (JAD) has risen to prominence as the preeminent publication devoted to studies of both AD and DM. This discovery emphasizes JAD's role as a medium for sharing pioneering studies in these areas. When looking at the best journals one by one, Frontiers in Endocrinology was clearly the best publication for DM studies. These findings highlight the vital role that these periodicals play in influencing the development of scientific discourse and the transmission of information in their respective fields.

Visualization:2

Fig (8) Distribution of publications related to Alzheimer's Disease & Diabetes Mellitus from 2003 to 2023

Fig (9) Distribution of publications pertaining with Alzheimer's Disease from 2003 to 2023

Fig (10) Distribution of publications pertaining with Diabetes Mellitus from 2003 to 2023

Start by importing the necessary libraries (glob for file management, pandas for data processing, matplotlib.pyplot for plotting, and seaborn for style) to produce the aforementioned graphic. The folder_path variable specifies the full path to the folder holding the CSV files. All CSV files in a certain folder are retrieved using glob in the code. To hold the merged CSV files' information, a new, blank DataFrame named combined_df is generated. The program loops over all CSV files, loads each one's contents into a DataFrame, and applies a filter based on the years 2003 through 2023. The concat function is then used to join the filtered data to the combined_df DataFrame.

The final DataFrame provides the needed information after processing all the CSV files. The code use the groupby function to divide the combined DataFrame into subsets based on publication year and then counts the total number of publications for each year. Using matplotlib.pyplot.plot, a line chart is drawn with the x-axis showing publishing years and the y-axis showing the total number of publications. Chart elements such as title and axis labels are finalized. Seaborn.despine is used to get rid of the spines (the lines that encircle the plot). Matplotlib.pyplot.grid is used to add a grid to the backdrop. Matplotlib.pyplot.show is responsible for displaying the chart.

The second diagram attempted to show where the many articles on AD and DM would appear between 2003 and 2023. The graph showed an overall rise in publications in both fields over time, reflecting the increasing focus on these disorders among researchers. After 2012, however, a greater number of studies sought to establish a link between Diabetes Mellitus and AD. There was a significant decline in the number of publications related to AD research after 2013, with a subsequent steady recovery beginning about 2015. On the other hand, there was no change in the publishing pace for DM research, with over 8000 papers appearing each year. This pattern highlights the ongoing importance of DM as a public health issue and the ongoing need for improvements in its treatment and prevention.

Visualization:3

Fig (11) Frequency of keywords pertaining with Alzheimer's Disease & Diabetes Mellitus over time (2003-2023)

Fig (12) Frequency of keywords related to Alzheimer's Disease over time (2003-2023)

Fig (13) Frequency of keywords related to Diabetes Mellitus over time (2003-2023)

The following plot was created by importing the glob and pandas libraries for file processing and the matplotlib.pyplot library for plotting. The location of the CSV files is given. To access all CSV files in the directory, the code makes advantage of the glob.glob method. The keyword frequencies are first stored in an empty dictionary called keyword_freq. Every CSV file is processed in turn by the code: It uses pd.read_csv to read the file. Used pd.to_datetime and comparison operations to narrow the time range to 2003-2023. goes over the filtered data row by row.

Verifies that the keywords column is both non-empty and non-null. Removes whitespace and separates terms with commas. Refreshes the keyword_freq dictionary by adding each keyword's frequency count. The keywords in the keyword_freq dictionary are ordered from most often to least. The 10 most often occurring terms are ranked highest and taken out. Top keywords serve as the x-values in a plt.plot line chart, while the keywords' frequencies serve as the y-values. A title, y-axis label, and x-axis label, as well as a rotated x-axis label, are added to the chart. By using plt.show(), the chart is shown.

The third chart showed how often certain terms and phrases linked to AD and DM were used during the 20 years. Alzheimer's disease, dementia, mild cognitive impairment, neurodegeneration, amyloid, and tau were the most frequently occurring terms in the scatter plot. These terms describe the main fields of study in AD, drawing attention to the most important pathogenic processes and molecular targets. Keywords including "Diabetes," "Type 2 Diabetes," "Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus," "Type 1 Diabetes," "Obesity," "Insulin Resistance," and "Inflammation" were particularly popular in discussions on DM. These terms cover several facets of diabetes mellitus, such as its many classifications, co-occurring conditions, and processes.

In conclusion, our study's findings illuminate the AD/DM research landscape by revealing the preeminent publications, authors, and keywords in the field. The visualizations showed the ever-changing nature of research trends, reflecting shifting attention and resources in various areas. These results have the potential to aid scientists and medical professionals in focusing their efforts, forming new partnerships, and designing more precise studies. This study adds to the larger effort to better understand, manage, and treat AD and DM, which should improve the quality of life for those who suffer from these conditions.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we used the PyMed library as an effective resource for mining information from PubMed, the world's largest database of scholarly articles. Our goal was to learn as much as possible about the literature by narrowing down on two common diseases: Alzheimer's and diabetes.

We carried out meticulous data cleansing methods to guarantee the quality of our results. We cleaned up the data by getting rid of duplicates, fixing any errors or missing information, and standardizing the variable types. Our

datasets' quality and integrity were greatly improved by this careful data cleaning method, laying a firm groundwork for further analysis.

The data visualizations we created were critical to conveying the significance of our results. We found the most important and frequently used phrases related to Alzheimer's disease and type 2 diabetes by analyzing the frequency of keywords. As a result of this study, academics, doctors, and politicians will be better equipped to set priorities, spot patterns, and design effective treatments.

Alzheimer's disease and diabetes mellitus research landscape was seen through the lens of time, thanks to the distribution of publications throughout time. To better understand the development and trends in these areas, we looked at the annual publication count. This analysis revealed both times of frenzied study and areas where more information is needed. Scientists may use this data to focus their exploration efforts and uncover previously unknown regions.

Furthermore, our analysis of the most prominent publications and writers in the field of Alzheimer's disease and diabetes mellitus research uncovered key opinion leaders and authoritative resources. Researchers can keep up with the newest developments more easily if they know which journals are the most influential, and can learn more about the areas of expertise of their favorite authors by studying their most cited works. With this information, scientists are better able to work together, share insights, and promote the spread of important results. Our findings have significant implications for the diagnosis and treatment of Alzheimer's disease and type 2 diabetes. Analysis of keyword frequency aids researchers in identifying core themes and ideas in the literature, which in turn helps them develop studies and therapies that target these illnesses' most crucial elements. These discoveries also help policymakers and healthcare professionals with decision-making and resource allocation.

In addition, looking at how articles have been published throughout time sheds light on how our understanding of Alzheimer's disease and type 2 diabetes has progressed. Stakeholders can better follow progress, pinpoint important discoveries, and evaluate the effects of policy and financing choices when they have a clear picture of the evolution of research through time. The obstacles presented by these illnesses cannot be overcome without this information, which is crucial for establishing evidence-based interventions. Our study aids researchers by highlighting the best journals and writers in the subject, making it easier for them to sift through the mountain of information. Sharing this information helps people work together, encourages innovative thinking across disciplines, and supports the development of new perspectives. Together, we can better control conditions like Alzheimer's and diabetes mellitus because of the speed with which we can make discoveries and implement treatments.

The significance of the study article extends well beyond the realm of academia. Improving the lives of individuals affected, bolstering the capabilities of researchers and doctors, and guiding policymakers in the development of successful measures is the ultimate goal of this in-depth examination of the link between Alzheimer's disease and diabetes mellitus. These results pave the way for more research into these disorders and improved methods of treatment, and they should spur continuous efforts to boost the quality of care and support provided to those who are afflicted by them. Future research advancements in the subject can only be achieved by building upon these results and encouraging multidisciplinary cooperation.

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